

Spectrophotometric Study of Copper and Thorium Complexes of Quinizarin-2-Sulphonic Acid

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Spectrophotometric study shows complex formation of quinizarin-sulphonic acid with Cu (II) in the ratio 1 : 1 and with Th (IV) in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (metal : reagent). Log K values of the complexes are respectively 3.3, 3.0 and 6.1 at 20°.

In continuation of our work on complexes of quinizarin-2-sulphonic acid (abbreviated as QSA) with Fe (III)¹ ion and UO₂ (II)² ion, it is observed that QSA reacts with Cu (II) ion to form a water soluble, brownish violet complex at pH 5.2 in the ratio 1 : 1. The copper complex has λ_{\max} at 480 m μ and is formed between pH 4.58 to 5.37. Similarly QSA reacts with Th (IV) ion to form pink (1 : 1) and purple (1 : 2; Th : QSA) complexes. The 1 : 1 thorium complex has λ_{\max} at 520 m μ and is formed upto pH 1.42, whereas 1 : 2 thorium complex has λ_{\max} at 570 m μ and is formed between pH 3.49 to 5.89. Thorium nitrate solution does not give any precipitate and QSA solution obeys Beer's law under the experimental conditions employed.

EXPERIMENTAL

QSA is of B.D.H. 'L.R.', CuSO₄·5H₂O, Th(NO₃)₄·6H₂O and NaCl are of B.D.H. 'Analar' and NaClO₄ is of B.D.H. 'chemically pure' quality. For buffer solutions, sodium acetate, KCl, HCl and acetic acid used are of either 'Analar' or 'chemically pure' quality. Buffer solutions are prepared either according to procedure adopted by Vogel³ or Findlay⁴. pH is adjusted by buffering 10 ml. of the mixed solutions (metal + reagent) with 2 ml. of the required buffer. For absorbance measurements, the experimental setup is the same as in our previous communications^{1,2}. All measurements are carried out after keeping the mixed solutions for about 3 hrs.

Nature of the Complexes Formed : Application of the method of Vosburgh and Cooper⁵ to the system CuSO₄-QSA (in the ratio 4 : 1, 2 : 1, 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 4 Cu²⁺ to QSA) keeping total volume 12 ml and pH 5.2 demonstrates the formation of one complex having λ_{\max} at 480 m μ under the experimental conditions. Likewise, thorium forms one pink complex (pH = 0.65 and λ_{\max} at 520 m μ) and one purple complex (pH = 5.0; λ_{\max} at 570 m μ).

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Effect of pH on the Absorbance and Composition of the Complexes : Absorbance (at 570 m μ , 580 m μ and 590 m μ) of solutions containing CuSO₄ and QSA (1 : 1) remains constant between pH 5.0 to 5.37 whereas absorbance (at 570 m μ , 580 m μ and 590 m μ) of solutions containing Th(NO₃)₄ and QSA (1 : 2) remains constant between pH 4.58 to 5.89. Application of Job's method of continued variations⁶ to the system of CuSO₄-QSA keeping total volume 12 ml (10 ml CuSO₄+QSA and 2 ml of the required buffer) shows that 1 : 1 complex is formed between pH 4.58 to 5.37. Similarly 1 : 1 thorium complex is formed below pH 2.0 and 1 : 2 thorium complex is formed between pH 3.49 and 5.89.

Stoichiometry of the Components : The stoichiometric ratio of the complexes has been established spectrophotometrically using Job's method⁶ of continued variations, mole-ratio method⁷ and slope-ratio method⁸.

pK valued by Mole-ratio Method : Log K values of the complexes, evaluated by the mole-ratio method are respectively 3.3, 3.0 and 6.1 at 20° for Cu-QSA complex and Th-QSA (1 : 1) and (1 : 2) complexes.

Molecular Extinction Coefficient by Slope-ratio Method : Molar extinction coefficient of the complexes, determined by slope ratio method at different wave lengths is as given in Table I.

TABLE I
Molar Extinction Coefficient of Copper and Thorium Complexes

Wave length	pH	Molar extinction coefficient $\times 10^2$
<i>Copper Complex</i>		
570 m μ	5.2	10.0
580 m μ	5.2	9.1
590 m μ	5.2	6.1
<i>Thorium Complex (1 : 1)</i>		
545 m μ	0.65	17.8
550 m μ	0.65	17.4
560 m μ	0.65	16.1
<i>Thorium Complex (1 : 2)</i>		
570 m μ	4.5 to 5.0	86.2
580 m μ	4.5 to 5.0	82.3
590 m μ	4.5 to 5.0	72.1

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